

Polar Occupancy Map - A Compact Traffic Representation for Deep Learning Scenario Classification

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Abstract—In order to accelerate development, testing and verification of automated vehicles, it is crucial to classify a wide range of driving scenarios. Scenario classification is usually done by rule-based algorithms or even manual video or signal inspection. A promising alternative is to use machine learning and let neural networks extract the relevant classification features. Since inputs to neural networks need to have a fixed size, an abstract representation of the driving scenario is necessary. In this paper, a scenario representation that captures the dynamic traffic behavior, without loss of relevant information, is presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to the enormous impact that vehicle automation will have on the future, the amount of interest and research in this area is steadily increasing. Research on Machine Learning (ML) and Computer Vision (CV) is driving forward great innovation in the field of autonomous vehicles, addressing many problems that were impossible to solve before. Furthermore, commercial vehicles already include various Automated Driving Functions (ADF). Currently, these functions focus on SAE level 2 autonomy [1], requiring a constant supervision of the driver in case of any emergency. However, to break this barrier and move to SAE levels 3 and 4 autonomy, where driver supervision is not required, the vehicle needs to be able to handle all possible situations properly.

Proving that a vehicle is able to act appropriately in all possible situations is not feasible because of the large number of external influences. Nevertheless, one way to evaluate autonomous vehicles is to verify that they are at least as safe as human drivers. In order to make a statistical proof, more than 240 million kilometers of driving is necessary [2]. This extensive driving validation is not achievable in a reasonable amount of time. Additionally, it would be necessary to repeat all test for every vehicle variant or software update. An even bigger problem is that whilst performing these test drives vehicles are mostly encountering already familiar scenarios, while new or critical scenarios appear rarely. A possible solution is to use simulation to validate most of the required miles and then take the vehicle on the real road. However, even in simulation we want to focus on the relevant measurements. With the Open Simulation Interface (OSI) [3],

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Fig. 1. Concept overview of the proposed scenario classification framework using the Polar Occupancy Map (POM) representation. The example scenario is a Target Ahead switch cut out.

it is possible to record both the real-world driving and the simulation in the same format. This makes it possible to develop a method using OSI which will cover both use cases. In addition, when relevant scenarios are extracted from the real world driving data, they can be imported into simulation where the scenario parameters can be changed to create more variations.

In this research we use the following terminology. A *scenario* is a high-level explanation of a traffic situation, e.g., a right lane change maneuver on a highway. A scenario definition by itself does not describe a specific traffic situation completely. From the scenario a *test case* can be derived providing defined parameter ranges, for example, right lane change maneuver on a highway with a lane change time from 3 to 5 seconds. Finally, a *test run* is a specific execution of a *test case* which is fully defined; for example, it could be a right lane change on a highway from the middle lane with a duration of 3.5 seconds.

The overall idea, shown in Fig. 1, is to apply Neural Networks (NN) on recorded driving data to extract relevant scenarios. The task of the NN is to look at specific *test runs* from the recordings, and learn how to group them in the correct scenario classes. By focusing only on the relevant scenarios and eliminating the known and unimportant ones, it is possible to significantly reduce current testing and validation times of ADFs [4], [5]. In addition, this method could be used to find and add new scenarios to a catalog of relevant scenarios.

Currently, scenario classification is mostly done manually or using rule-based algorithms. The manual extraction is done by engineers during the test drive or directly on the recorded data. Even though manual extraction of relevant scenarios provides high accuracy, it requires a lot of effort and time. On the other hand, rule-based methods use predefined triggers and patterns that are matched against the data.

Complicated scenarios require great effort to define all the necessary rules.

As a lot of the recorded driving data is already available, it is possible to use NNs to learn the required features and underlying scenario rules. This approach is highly scalable as new scenarios can be added by retraining, and once the scenarios are learned, the network can be easily deployed and used on new data.

However, there is an intrinsic challenge with NNs that needs to be addressed. The feature input size of a NN has to be constant and independent of the current scenario and number of participants. Furthermore, to create a robust classifier the input should be independent from the order of the participants to avoid generating different scenarios when the motion of the participants is the same. In this paper, we focus on a novel compact representation that satisfies the requirements and relies on sensor fusion information, i.e., object lists. The proposed method creates a Polar Occupancy Map (POM) representation of the scenario. The benefits of such an approach are a huge reduction in the input size and an abstract representation that can be used on a variety of traffic scenarios.

As a proof of concept, we focus on detecting and classifying most common highway scenarios. The scenarios are categorized in 9 classes: Driving in lane, Lane change, Ego free lane cut in, Ego free lane cut out, Target Ahead (TA) free lane cut in, TA free lane cut out, TA switch cut in, TA switch cut out.

II. RELATED WORK

Scenario classification has been addressed by several research groups in the recent years. The methodologies used for scenario classification can be divided into two major groups: model-based classification and classification using ML. Regarding the model-based approach, Elrofai *et al.* [6] have used a vehicle model to estimate the yaw rate using a minimal number of basic sensors. The estimated yaw rate is filtered and together with other parameters it is used to classify turn and lane change scenarios. The difference of the proposed POM approach is that it considers other traffic participants and does not rely solely on the internal measurements of the ego vehicle.

The ML approach can be further divided into image and time-series based classification. Image-based classification was addressed by Kastner *et al.* [7] and Bernini *et al.* [8]. The two research groups proposed similar methods in which they use static images to classify the current type of surrounding the vehicle is in. Both groups divide the image into 16 equal parts, transforming each sub-part into the frequency domain and use ML methods for the classification. Kastner *et al.* proposed a Hierarchical Principal Component Classification (HPCC) that uses a 400×300 image to classify whether the vehicle is currently located on a highway, country road or inner city. Similarly, Bernini *et al.* used a 256×256 image to classify urban, highway and rural driving. They did a comparison between Principal Component Analysis (PCA),

Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) and Support Vector Machines (SVM). The limit of this approach is that it cannot capture the dynamic behavior of the traffic and it mainly focuses on the surrounding to make the prediction of the scenario type.

In our previous work [9], we used time-series data recorded from the ego vehicle's sensors and NNs in order to classify scenarios relevant for a Lane Keep Assist System. However, other traffic participants were not taken in consideration.

Roesener *et al.* [10] worked also on time-series classification of scenarios and applied it on the assessment of automated driving. They used extracted features, e.g., Time to Collision (TTC), Time to Next Cut In (TTNCI), TTC and TTNCI derivatives etc., to classify four classes: Lane Change, Vehicle Following, Free driving and Cut In. They compared the performance of the following methods: Naive Bayes, ADABOOST Simple Tree and Median Tree.

Cara *et al.* [11] used time-series data to classify critical car-cyclist scenarios. The input for their proposed method was the cyclist trajectory and ego vehicle velocity and acceleration. They used 99 recordings that were filtered to ensure that a cyclist was included.

Even though Roesener and Cara *et al.* consider dynamic behavior of other participants, the proposed approaches are limited to only one participant per recording. In addition, they use the distinct information of the participant to create the features needed for the classification. In our approach, we explore how the information of an arbitrary number of participants can be represented and used as input to a NN.

A representation of driving scenarios that can capture the dynamic behavior of an arbitrary number of participants was introduced by Gruner *et al.* [12]. They have used a top view Grid Map (GM) approach and proposed three types of maps: Velocity Grid (VeG), Stacked Velocity Grid (SVeG) and History Grid (HiG). The VeG is a 3 channel map where the first channel represents a binary occupancy, i.e., whether an object is present or not, and the other two channels capture the object's v_x and v_y velocity components. Both the SVeG and HiG are based on the VeG. The SVeG is a stacked representation of two VeGs separated by some Δt leading to a 6 channel representation. The HiG representation fuses several VeGs by fading the occupancy channel of older time-steps and uses the last VeG for the two remaining channels. All maps use 50×50 pixels per channel, with a resolution of 1 pixel per meter in the longitudinal and 2 pixels per meter in the lateral direction. In other words, to capture a single time-step, the VeG requires $3 \times 50 \times 50 = 7500$ inputs. The HiG requires the same amount for an arbitrary number of time-steps; however, because of the fusion of several VeGs it is not possible to avoid information loss. For example, if a vehicle moves right (*motion-1*) and then left again (*motion-2*) the whole motion would not be visible as *motion-2* overwrites *motion-1*. The SVeG requires double the amount of inputs as VeG and introduces information loss depending on the size of Δt .

Fig. 2. Design of the Polar Occupancy Map representation. a) For each time-step t_i the field of view of all vehicles is transformed from the local ego coordinate system (x, y) to a new coordinate system $(f(d, v_d, g(\sigma)), \varphi)$. b) The φ axis tracks the amount of the visual field all vehicles take. On the vertical axis we introduce a general function (f) which is used to manipulate the attention of the NN. Considering the classes we want to recognize, we chose as an input the distance d from the ego vehicle, together with the ego lateral velocity v_d and a scaled Gaussian function $g(\sigma)$. c) This representation is a top view of figure b), where the value of the function $f(d, v_d, g(\sigma))$ is denoted by color - yellow corresponds to higher and green to lower values. d) By stacking the representations from c) we get a distinct trace through time which can be used as an input for the NN. Note that figure d) shows traces for all intermediate time-steps which were not shown in previous figures.

We propose a completely different method for encoding the dynamic behavior of traffic participants called Polar Occupancy Map. The POM requires only 270 inputs per time step to capture the closest traffic participants without loss of relevant information. This leads to a size reduction of factor 27 per time-step compared to the VeG representation.

Our work shares some resemblance with the Vector Field Histogram (VFH) proposed by Borenstein *et al.* [13]. They have used the field of view to create a polar histogram density function for robot navigation. Even though the proposed representation also uses the field of view approach, we do not use the histogram representation for the horizontal axis but propose a new function that is used to manipulate the attention of the neural network. In addition, the representations are stacked to track the traffic motion through time. The next section will give an in-depth explanation of the proposed approach.

III. POLAR OCCUPANCY MAP

The POM approach is based on the idea that the dynamic behavior of traffic participants can be tracked by measuring the field of view that each vehicle is occupying. This process is shown in Fig. 2.

The design of the POM representation starts with the ego vehicle's local coordinate system (x, y) as shown in Fig. 2 a). This scenario contains two vehicles. The first vehicle is performing a left lane change entering the lane of the ego vehicle. The second vehicle is driving on a free lane left to the ego vehicle. In order to track the movements of the vehicles, three time-steps t_0, t_1, t_2 are shown. The field of view of the ego vehicle starts at the x -axis, or zero radians, and changes to π in the clockwise and $-\pi$ in the counter clockwise direction. For each time-step, the slices of the field of view φ_i that each vehicle occupies are recorded. This is denoted with light red color in the figure. Please note that for clarity only some slices of the field of view were colored.

The recorded fields of view for each vehicle can be visualized in a 2D plot as shown in Fig. 2 b). In this subfigure, three plots that correspond to the three time-steps

t_0, t_1, t_2 are shown. The horizontal axis is the field of view φ given in radians, and the vertical axis is a generic function f . This function is used to manipulate the attention of the NN and is chosen such that it aids the network in finding the extraction features. Considering the classes we want to recognize in this research, the minimal distance to the vehicle and the lateral velocity of the ego vehicle are used as arguments.

The focus of the network should be on vehicles that are closest to the ego vehicle and are in the same lane. Furthermore, the NN needs to distinguish if the motion in the representation is coming from the traffic or from the ego vehicle. In other words, because the representation is based on the ego vehicle's local frame, without the information of the lateral movement NNs would not be able to differentiate between movements of other vehicles and the movement of the ego vehicle. By following these design choices, the function f is defined as:

$$\hat{d}_i = k \cdot d_i + n \quad (1)$$

$$f_i(d_i, v_d, g(\sigma)) = \hat{d}_i + |v_d| + g(\sigma) \quad (2)$$

where d_i is the minimal distance to the vehicle in $[m]$, v_d is the ego vehicle's lateral velocity in $[\frac{m}{s}]$, and k and n are coefficients that create a linear transform of the distance d_i . Vehicles are recorded to the POM representation if the distance is less than 75m. Which bounds d_i to $[0, 75)$. The coefficients k and n are chosen such that the value \hat{d}_i is bounded between 0 and 1, and when the distance d_i decreases the new value \hat{d}_i increases, i.e., k is negative. This effectively shifts the attention of the neural network to vehicles that are closer to the ego vehicle. The coefficients are chosen as $k = -0.011$ and $n = 1$. The inverted distance \hat{d}_i is only applied when a vehicle is present, whereas the lateral velocity v_d is applied on the whole representation making it possible to detect lane changes when no vehicles are visible. The last argument is the function g which is a scaled Gaussian function centered around zero degrees, where $\sigma = 0.005$ and $\max(g(\sigma)) \approx 0.9$. This function is only applied if a

vehicle is visible and is located around zero degrees, giving it a higher value and turning the focus of the network to it.

The summation of \hat{d}_i and the absolute value of v_d could mean that a vehicle is either close to the ego vehicle or that the ego vehicle itself is moving. This will not be a problem in our representation for two reasons. First, if the vehicle is really close to the ego we will know it by the size of the field of view, as closer vehicles have wider fields of view and vice versa. Second, if there is lateral movement of the ego vehicle then all fields of view are moving which can be detected and distinguished by the NN. Furthermore, the summation could also be interpreted as information loss. However, the task of the network is to detect scenarios and report at which time-step they occurred. If the exact state values of the traffic participants are needed, one could easily go to the specific time-step and read it from the available data.

At this step we have already created a representation with a fixed feature size. The 2D plots could be stacked creating a 3D plot with a fixed number of time-steps that can be used as an input to the network. However, in the recent years there has been a significant breakthrough in pattern recognition using Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [14]. That is why we use a top view of the 2D plots, as shown in Fig. 2 c), and stack them in such a way to create an image. The color of the pixels corresponds to the value of the function $f_i(d_i, v_d, g(\sigma))$. By filling in the missing time-steps and assigning a value of zero to non-occupied parts of the field of view, we obtain the final form of the representation as shown in Fig. 2 d).

Examining the final image, it can be seen that the vehicles create unique traces which are recorded by the POM representation without loss of relevant information. Finally, the traces can be detected and distinguished by the CNN, leading to accurate classifications.

In this approach, there are two further benefits for the extraction of relevant information that need to be addressed. The first one is that for vehicles that are far away from the ego vehicle the occupied angle is getting smaller. This naturally leads the network to not focus on them. In addition, because we are more interested on what is happening in front and on the sides of the ego vehicle than in the back, we use different resolutions for the POM representation. A resolution of 4 pixels per degree is used on the front from -10° to 10° , 1 pixel per degree on the sides from -30° to -10° and 10° to 30° . Finally, 0.5 pixels per degree on the back -180° to -30° and 30° to 180° . This selection of resolutions leads to the final size of 270 values per time-step for the POM representation.

The second benefit is that only the first vehicle that occupies a certain field of view is recorded. As we are mostly interested in the closest vehicles, this further decreases the amount of information whilst preserving the relevant parts. In addition, if the ego vehicle is only equipped with camera sensors than this behavior occurs automatically.

IV. DATA GENERATION

In order to train a neural network, a lot of training examples are required. This is generally a very time-consuming task as we first need to record the data and then label it accordingly. However, because we are using an abstract representation of the environment, which can be replicated in simulation easily, we decided to generate synthetic labeled data for training and then apply the trained NN to real recordings. This way only a subset of recorded data needs to be labeled for validation.

The simulation environment consists of a 3 lane highway with 3 to 4 participants including the ego vehicle. The generated data is divided into 9 most common highway scenarios as shown in Fig. 3 a).

The classes are:

- 1) **Driving in lane** - The ego vehicle is driving in a lane and there are no maneuvers from other vehicles.
- 2) **Lane change** - The ego vehicle is switching between free adjacent lanes.
- 3) **Ego free lane cut in** - The ego vehicle is cutting in from a free to an occupied lane.
- 4) **Ego free lane cut out** - The ego vehicle is cutting out from an occupied to a free lane.
- 5) **Ego cut in-out** - The ego vehicle is moving between two occupied lanes, hence making a cut in-out.
- 6) **Target ahead (TA) free lane cut in** - A vehicle is cutting in from a free lane to the ego vehicle's lane.
- 7) **TA free lane cut out** - A vehicle is cutting out from ego vehicle's lane to a free lane.
- 8) **TA switch cut in** - A vehicle is cutting in between the ego and another vehicle which leads to the switch of the current TA.
- 9) **TA switch cut out** - A vehicle which was between the ego and another vehicle cuts out to a free lane leading to a switch of the current TA.

All classes should be detected by the neural network irrespective of the shape of the highway. This is achieved by using the Frenet-Serret frame instead of a global frame. The used Frenet-Serret frame is defined by the axis s denoting the length of the path traveled on the highway and axis d denoting the orthogonal distance from the middle of the highway. In other words, the transformation between the global and Frenet-Serret frame decouples the motion of the vehicles from the shape of the highway.

To calculate the transformation from the global to the Frenet-Serret frame, information about the highway curvature is needed. This information is usually available from a map in which the vehicle is localized using Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS). Alternatively, a camera system could be used to enhance the curvature measurement by tracking the road or lane marking curvatures.

In addition, the yaw rate of the ego vehicle relative to the Frenet-Serret frame will influence the POM representation. However, in this use case it was regarded as noise because the relative yaw rate is small on highways and occurs only in the ego lane change scenarios.

Fig. 3. a) Scenario classes b) Randomly generated scenarios (3., 7. and 8.) with a duration of 7 seconds. Each column consists of a scatter plot showing the motion of the ego vehicle (blue-green) and other participants (red-yellow) on the highway, and the corresponding POM representation. c) First channel of the HiG grid map for the same scenarios as in b).

Fig. 3 b) and c) show 3 randomly generated scenarios. The scatter plot shows the motion of the ego vehicle (blue-green) and other participants (red-yellow) during 7 seconds in the highway’s Frenet-Serret frame. The images below show the corresponding POM representations. Fig. 3 c) shows the first channel of the HiG representations for the same scenarios as in b). The HiG’s first channel is an aggregation of VeGs constructed for each time-step. The VeG size is fixed to $60 \times 20 \times 3$ and the ego center point is moved back to give more focus to the front of the vehicle. The resolution of the VeG is two meters per pixel on the x and one meter per pixel on the y axis.

For each generated scenario, starting positions, lanes, maneuvers, and velocities are generated randomly but satisfy several conditions to assure that the specific scenario is possible. Furthermore, uniform noise was added to the motion of the vehicles to generate more realistic scenarios.

In the first scenario, Fig. 3 b, c), a right cut in maneuver by the ego vehicle is shown. There are two constraints in this case. First, the ego vehicle cannot be on the right most lane because a right lane change would not be possible. And secondly, there should be a vehicle in front in the desired lane. Similar constraints apply to all scenarios.

In the second scenario, a TA free lane cut out is shown. It is important to notice the difference between the values of the $f(d, v_d, g(\sigma))$ function for this and the previous scenario. In this case, the ego vehicle’s lateral velocity v_d is zero and the function $f(d, v_d, g(\sigma))$ only depends on the distance and the g function. However, in the first scenario the ego vehicle had lateral velocity and we can see in the POM representation that a unique pattern was created. Without this pattern it would be impossible to distinguish the first scenario from a cut in scenario.

The third scenario represents a TA switch cut in. Examining the POM representation, it can be seen that there was a vehicle in front of the ego vehicle and after some time a new vehicle made a cut in. Furthermore, we notice how the function $g(\sigma)$ is highlighting the vehicle which is near zero degrees, i.e., in the ego vehicle’s lane.

For certain scenarios it is enough to have one other participant together with the ego vehicle, e.g., TA free cut in. However, an additional vehicle which was randomly

positioned on the highway was used. This was done in order to teach the network to ignore other vehicles if they are not relevant to the desired classes. It is important to note that in simulation we will never be able to cover all possible scenarios that can occur in the real world. However, ML driven approaches give us the ability to iteratively improve the models. With time, we will be able to find out scenario where the models are uncertain and where more training is necessary.

In total, we created 15000 random scenarios where 10% is used for the test and 10% for the validation set. Each scenario has a duration of 20 seconds with a sampling rate of $10Hz$. The labels are generated automatically for each time-step. The generated data includes the proposed POM representation together with the Grid Map representations VeG, SVeG and HiG, which are going to be used for performance comparison. Please note that the scenario generation code, network implementations, and training data are open-source and can be found at [15].

V. CLASSIFICATION USING DEEP LEARNING

The proposed POM approach creates a representation which is suitable for training Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN). These networks excel in extracting features and recognizing patterns in images. However, to increase the performance compared to the classical CNNs [14], we used several enhancements introduced in recent studies.

Dilated Convolutions were proposed by Yu *et al.* [16] and the main idea is to increase the receptive field of the CNN without adding additional layers. The problem with additional layers is that they increase the overall size of the network and are much harder to train. In a normal convolutional network, the receptive field increases linearly with each layer; however, if we introduce kernel dilation, we can achieve an exponential increase of the receptive field.

K. He *et al.* [17] worked on *Residual Connections* to mitigate the vanishing gradient problem. They introduced skip connections between layers allowing the gradients to propagate more easily through the network. In addition, Veit *et al.* [18] argue that the residual connections increase accuracy because they allow the information to flow through more paths.

Fig. 4. Evaluation of the POM representation on real data using the Mobileye[®] camera. Each column shows a camera frame and its corresponding POM representation with a window size of 50 samples. The white dashed line shows the middle of the sliding windows where the prediction is made. The sequence shows a TA free lane cut in.

The final enhancements that were used are the *Self Normalizing Layers* and *Alpha Dropout*. It is widespread practice to normalize the input data into the network. However, during the training individual layers of the network can change the distribution slowing down the learning process. One solution would be to use *Batch Normalization* after each layer, proposed by Ioffe *et al.* [19]. This approach, however, adds additional complexity to the network. A different solution was proposed by Klambauer *et al.* [20] where a new activation function called *SELU* was introduced. With the new activation function, outputs from each layer converge to a zero mean and unit variance without any additions. If dropout is necessary, then *Alpha Dropout* [20] is used to preserve the output distribution.

The proposed neural network consists of 9 convolutional layers, combining dilation and residual connections. The convolutional layers represent the feature extraction and are followed by 4 dense layers producing the class probabilities. Each layer uses the *SELU* activation, and *Alpha Dropout* with a dropout rate of 10% is used on the final dense layers. For the evaluation, 50 time-steps, i.e., POM representations, were used leading to the final input size of 50×270 values. The full network architecture is given in Table I.

VI. RESULTS

The performance of the POM based neural network is evaluated in two steps. First, we will compare its ability to extract the desired classes against the Grid Map based models introduced by Gruner *et al.* [12], namely SVeG and HiG. In addition to these two representations, we also introduced a fully stacked VeG model which we call FVeG and a regular

TABLE I
MODEL ARCHITECTURE

layer	kernel	stride	dilation	residual	input size
conv1	3×3	1×1	1×1	no	$50 \times 270 \times 1$
conv2	3×3	1×2	1×1	no	$50 \times 135 \times 32$
conv3	3×3	1×1	1×1	yes	$50 \times 135 \times 32$
conv4	3×3	1×2	1×1	no	$50 \times 68 \times 32$
conv5	3×3	1×1	2×1	no	$50 \times 68 \times 32$
conv6	3×3	2×2	1×1	no	$25 \times 34 \times 64$
conv7	3×3	1×1	4×1	yes	$25 \times 34 \times 64$
conv8	3×3	2×2	1×1	no	$13 \times 17 \times 128$
conv9	3×3	2×2	1×1	no	$7 \times 17 \times 128$
dense layers	conv8	dense1	dense2	dense3	dense4
size	8064	1024	512	256	9

TABLE II
TRAINING RESULTS

accuracy	SVeG	HiG	FVeG	POM-CNN	POM
test	87.76%	85.04%	93.82%	95.26%	96.17%
validation	88.10%	85.70%	94.80%	95.30%	96.00%

CNN network (POM-CNN) without residual connections and dilation. The second step is an evaluation of the trained model on real object data captured by the Mobileye[®] camera. The camera is placed on the front of the vehicle and has a total field of view of around 90° . The simulation data was adjusted to match the field of view of the camera and make the data more realistic.

The generated training data consist of 15000 scenarios with a duration of 20s and a sampling rate of $10Hz$. For each sample the POM and VeG representations are created. To process the whole scenario, a sliding window approach is used. The window size is fixed to 50 time-steps and the networks generate the predictions in the middle of the window. This prediction scheme gives the networks the ability to take into consideration past and future samples in order to produce the correct class label, leading to higher accuracy. The sliding window is moved across the whole scenario generating the class probabilities for each subsequent time-step.

The SVeG model uses the first and last VeG from a given window. The HiG model aggregates all VeGs occupancy in the first channel and uses the remaining 2 channels from the last VeG in the window. The FVeG stacks together all VeGs from a given window leading to the largest input size of $60 \times 20 \times 3 \times 50$.

The POM, HiG, SVeG and FVeG networks share the same architecture from Table I with different input sizes. The POM-CNN uses the same number of layers but does not include residual connections or dilation. All networks were trained for 2304 steps using a batch size of 128 windows and a decaying learning rate. The networks were initialized using the variance-scaling initializer [21] and optimized with the ADAM [22] optimizer.

Table II shows the performance of the models on the test and validation set. We can see that the SVeG and HiG models have the lowest performance. The drawback of the SVeG model is that it only uses the first and last VeG from a window which leads to significant information loss. The HiG model does aggregate the occupancy of other vehicles; however, because of the way the HiG representation is constructed some information can still be lost as parts of previous maneuvers can be overwritten with the more recent ones. The FVeG representation performs much better

because all time-steps of the sliding window are visible to the network. However, the drawback of the FVeG representation is the big input size and longer training times. The proposed POM models have both the best test and validation accuracy. With residual connections and dilation, the POM network shows better performance compared to the regular POM-CNN. Moreover, the POM network uses a 27 times smaller input than the FVeG.

Finally, the POM network was evaluated on real object data obtained with the Mobileye[®] camera. The test run was done on the A9 highway near Graz, Austria. A sample TA free lane cut in scenario from the recorded data is shown in Fig. 4. Each column shows the camera frame and the corresponding POM representation for the current time window. We can see how the motion of the cutting-in vehicle is tracked through the representation. The performance of the pre-trained POM model was evaluated using 2900 sequential time windows. The recordings contained curves and they were compensated using the camera's lane curvature information. In order for a scenario to be extracted, the model certainty for that scenario needed to be higher than 95%. With this extraction method we were able to lower the misclassifications and obtain an overall detection accuracy of 90.8%. All data and models used in this research are open-source and available at [15].

VII. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

In this paper, we introduced a novel traffic representation that can be used to train neural networks for scenario classification. As the input size to the neural network needs to be constant, we designed a representation that is independent from the number of traffic participants in the scenario. The representation is based on the polar occupancy map and we have shown that it is capable of creating unique patterns which can be used for scenario classification. To evaluate the representation, a Convolutional Neural Network was trained on 9 highway scenarios, resulting in high classification accuracy. The proposed model was compared to existing traffic representations, showing that it offers improved performance with a more compact representation. Finally, we have shown that the model trained on simulated data has generalized well and that it can be used to make high accuracy predictions on real data.

Our next steps will include improvements of the simulation in order to classify an even broader range of scenarios and taking into consideration the ego vehicle's yaw rate relative to the road.

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